

Formation of *N*-(*p*-Sulphamoylbenzyl-)phthalimide

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Kusami *et al.*¹ reported the preparation of *N*-(*p*-sulphamoylbenzyl-)phthalimide (I) in connection with their work on homosulphanilamide (II). Now we have encountered the formation of (I) under the following conditions.

When a dilute, faintly alkaline solution (about 5%) of *N*¹-acetyl-*N*⁴-phthalylsulphanilamide (III) was allowed to mix with a neutral aqueous solution of compound (II), the resulting clear solution slowly developed turbidity at the room temperature and precipitation was virtually complete after a brief period of reflux. It was, however, obtained in almost quantitative yield (*vide infra*).

The isolated compound, m.p. 221-22°, is practically insoluble in cold water and moderately soluble in hot ethanol. It remains unaffected by cold sodium carbonate solution or boiling 6*N*-HCl. It readily dissolves in 10% NaOH solution from which it is regenerated on acidification; but prolonged boiling provides small quantities of phthalic acid.

These properties, coupled with molecular weight determination, spectral data, and elemental analysis, suggested structure (I) for the above compound. Conclusive evidence was obtained by mixed m.p. determination and superimposable absorption curve with an authentic sample.

Formation of compound (I) from (II) and (III) therefore involves *S_N2* type of reaction with concomitant loss of *N*¹-acetyl from (III) and formation of the imide ring. This is consistent with stronger nucleophilic character of ArCH₂NH₂ over ArNH₂. *Conclusions*

support to this contention was achieved as follows. Equimolar amounts of compounds (IV) and (V), when heated together, virtually provided quantitative yield of *N*-benzylphthalimide, m.p. 116°, but the reverse reaction could not be detected. The following reaction path therefore could be visualised for the displacement reaction between (IV) and (V).

Formation of *N*-(*p*-sulphamoylbenzyl)-phthalimide (I)

(a). A mixture of compounds (III) (0.02*M*, 7.25 g.) and (II) (0.02 *M*, 4.45 g.) was suspended in water (100 ml). An aqueous solution (20%) of NaOH was slowly added with cooling until pH was about 7.2. The clear solution was then refluxed for an hour, cooled, and the white crystals were collected, washed with water, and dried; m.p. 221-22°, yield 5 g. Further crystallisation from ethanol did not raise the m.p. (Found: N, 8.94. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 8.86%). M.W. (Rast), 330.

$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 225 μ (log ϵ , 4.72); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ (cm $^{-1}$) 3360w, 3265 w (-NH-); 2917 s, 2850 m (-CH $_2$ -); 1700 s (-CO-); 1310 m, 1115 m (-SO-) $^{\circ}$.

(b). An authentic sample of compound (I) obtained under (A) was prepared as follows. A mixture of phthalic anhydride (2.5 g.) and hydrochloride of compound (II) (3.76 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. in presence of fused sodium acetate (2.2 g.) After working up in the usual way, 5.2 g. of the material, m.p. 221-22°, was obtained (lit 1 . m.p. 222-23°).

Reaction between N-Phenylphthalimide and Benzylamine.—A mixture of *N*-phenylphthalimide $^{\circ}$ (1.0 g.), m.p. 204-205°, and benzylamine (0.48 g.) was heated under reflux

for 30 min. at 210-20°. After cooling and trituration with dilute acetic acid, 1.02 g. of the product, m.p. 110-16°, was obtained. Melting point was raised to 116° after crystallisation from dilute acetic acid; no depression in mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of (VI), prepared according to Vogel³, was observed.

As stated before, *N*-benzylphthalimide was recovered unchanged when it was heated with aniline under the above conditions.

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3. Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 569, 1959 impression.